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The Intra-School Crime as an Important Influencing Factor on Students' Psychology and its Prediction by Using Artificial Neural Networks

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Abstract

Intra-school crime is a very important factor that affects students' psychology at school. The phenomenon of in-school crime can be interpreted by taking into account various parameters. These parameters may be related to family and biological factors, as well as socio-economic parameters but also to individual factors such as social values and cognitive beliefs. The consequences of the intra-school violence acts on victims are often psychologically and physically painful. The physical damage that a student experiences from the physical violence and the mental injury may badly stigmatize his or her psychosis. School bullying and school violence can also cause a student to refuse to go to school or to permanently abandon it. In addition, the psychological pressure suffered by the pupils - victims leads them to depression, anxiety and feelings of

discomfort. This research has studied the data of several years regarding school crime. Also, predictions of crime rates were made by using artificial neural networks. Neural network prediction models were developed by studying various socio-economic factors that could affect the intra-school crime. Neural network models were trained by investigating various neural topologies and training algorithms. The final prediction results have showed a fairly good accuracy. This research can help the relevant public services to implement the appropriate guidelines and strategies to prevent and combat the intra-school violence, which is a very important factor that affects students' psychology.